

STUDY HABITS AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AMONG NURSING STUDENTS AT PRIVATE UNIVERSITY PESHAWAR: A CORRELATIONAL STUDY

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Abstract

Introduction

The study habits of learners are the key aspects that affect their academic achievement. Inappropriate study habits are considered as a primary factor contributing to students' academic failure and can significantly affect their educational and professional potential.

Objectives

To assess the study habits amongst the nursing student enrolled at the Institute of Nursing Sciences, Sarhad University of Science and Information Technology, Peshawar.

1. To find out the relationship between study habits and academic performance amongst nursing students enrolled at the Institute of Nursing Sciences, Sarhad University of Science and Information Technology, Peshawar.

Methodology

This research uses a correlational study design. The research was conducted at the Institute of Nursing Sciences (INS), Sarhad University of Information Technology and Science, Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

Results

The result revealed that desirable study habits of the students was 37.92%. The Majority of relatively study habits of the students were 58.33%. Academic performance among nursing students, majority were showing 59.24% which indicate good academic performance of the students. The result also revealed as (-.006 and p-value=0.924) very weak negative association between study habits and academic performance.

Conclusion

The present study aimed to assess study habits and academic performance among BS nursing students. Majority of the students were having relatively study habits. Academic performance amongst nursing students, majority were showing good academic performance of the students. Overall, a very weak negative relationship was found between study habits and academic performance in our research study. Future research should include participants from multiple universities.

INTRODUCTION

STUDY HABITS

Study habits are referred to as the routine method of studying which also impacts cognitive processes. Study habits involve various tasks, including time management, choosing a suitable study environment, goal setting, efficient note-taking strategies, and arranging the study routine (Khan, 2021). The study habits of learners are the key components that affect their academic achievement. Inadequate study habits are seen as the main factor contributing to students' academic failure, significantly affecting their education and career potential (Akter et al., 2023). The majority of students revealed that study techniques and habits significantly influence learning and academic performance. A wide range of students use study aids for examination preparation, such as summaries, charts, tables, or notes, created by themselves or others (Bakre & Abdelmgied, 2024). Effective methods of study along with appropriate resources are crucial for achieving academic performance. The relationship between study habits and academic performance is complex and requires comprehensive understanding (Osama et al., 2024). Certain students may possess ineffective study habits that frustrate them and contribute to learning challenges. A crucial element of education is the development of efficient study habits. Adhering to a consistent timetable and equitably addressing each subject are fundamental elements of effective study practices (Princy et al., 2023).

ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

Academic performance is a capability achieved by students in school, college, and university through time spent in classrooms, laboratories, or libraries. Enhancement of academic performance results in academic achievement; an improvement in academics. achievement results in national development and the delivery of efficient forces (Rezaie Looyeh et al., 2017). Performance pressure may originate from unattainable and unrealistic expectations from family, outside factors, or even personal goals. Regardless of the cause, it has been proven to be detrimental to the mental health of a student. Moreover, fear and stress are not good, not only

to the student but also to the student's grades as well. These two can be damaging to the academic performance of many students (Jasa et al., 2024). According to a study; Students achieving higher academic results participated in regular study sessions of approximately 2-4 hours daily, maintained focus for 1-2 hours consecutively, preferred changing study locations, and integrated breaks of approximately 30 minutes, with their study habits being consistent during holidays (Mushtaq, 2022).

STUDY HABITS IN NURSING STUDENTS

Nursing students have exerted significant effort in their clinical practice and participation in nursing organizations throughout the semesters to improve their grades and ranking. Therefore, individuals encounter psychological issues that impair their functioning. ("Determinants of Stress and Its Association with Academic Performance of Undergraduate Students of Nursing in Pakistan," 2023). Nursing education encompasses theoretical learning and clinical responsibilities, demanding that students experience various assessments and procedures. Nursing students engage with patients during clinical tasks, fulfilling the roles of care provider, health promoter, advocate, and collaborator with patients and other healthcare professionals. (Khan et al., 2022). The diversity of student cohorts and the process of internationalization heighten the demands placed on nursing academics to address students' needs and preferences, thereby fostering understanding and creating an effective curriculum that enhances learning outcomes. Understanding learning styles and preferences can enhance faculty awareness of student diversity, hence facilitating the development of learning experiences that align with these styles. (Mohammadi et al., 2017). According to a research study, students who use note taking while learning can remember study materials longer. In addition, they write down key points, which lead to better understanding. On the other hand, students who do not take notes, copy their classmates' notes in order to be prepared for exams, which cause undesirable academic performances (Rezaie Looyeh et al., 2017). Similarly, an another study by (Jasa et al., 2024) concluded that the study habits have no

significance on the academic performance among student nurses suggests that variations in study habits do not significantly impact their academic outcomes. Despite individual differences in study habits, student nurses exhibit a consistent pattern in their approaches to studying, as evidenced by the lack of significant correlation with academic performance. A research study conducted at College of Nursing, Cebu Normal University revealed that the nursing students had a rating of good in their academic performance and the main factors which affect the academic performance of nursing students are the study habits and learning styles. Based upon this study the researcher recommended that "If academic performance is to be improved, the learning styles and study habits of the students must first be improved" (Daño, 2015). A study by (Khalili, 2018) also revealed that the Study habits in 86.9% of students were relatively good, in 6.8% favorable, and in 4.5% of them were poor while there was a significant positive relationship between mean score study habits and academic performance. Similarly in the context of Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa; a study conducted by ("Determinants of Stress and Its Association with Academic Performance of Undergraduate Students of Nursing in Pakistan," 2023) concluded that moderate stress is a problem for undergraduate nursing students and the most mentioned causes of stress are still "workload and assignments," "stress due to environment," and "stress from taking care of patients. Another descriptive correlational study among undergraduate nursing students of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa revealed that there is no correlation between stress and academic achievement. Compared to female students, male students have more exposure to stress due to the burden of study and domestic responsibilities. Stress among first-year undergraduate nursing students is common due to exposure to medical and health subjects. With the passage of time, nursing students manage stress with the help of coping strategies (Sultan et al., 2022). Academic success is having a great importance in each student's life. Every student's desire is to score good marks in examination but everyone is not able to achieve the same level of success in examination. There

are various factors which include lack of motivation, inadequate guidance from mentors, stress due to great competition, support from parents etc. Therefore, this study examine; to assess the study habits and find out correlation between study habits and academic performance among nursing students at Institute of Nursing Sciences, Sarhad University of Science & Information Technology, Peshawar aiming to identify effective strategies for improved learning outcomes. Insights from this study can help educators refine teaching methods, enhance student support systems, and align curriculum development with learning preferences, ultimately contributing to the development of competent healthcare professionals.

LITERATURE REVIEW

ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN GLOBAL VIEW

Academic performance is a key indicator of their cognitive development, learning abilities, and overall educational success. Numerous elements impact it, such as mental health, family dynamics, motivation, cognitive abilities, and the quality of instruction (Thomas). According to a study by (Alex et al.); Effective study techniques, time management, and self-discipline can help nursing students better understand complex subjects, retain information, and perform well academically. Nursing students' study habits have significant impacts on their academic performance. Similarly, another study by (Princy et al., 2023) concluded that the majority of students had good and average study habits, and that they performed well academically, achieving first-class grades. Thus, it motivates us to implement nursing interventions to enhance the academic performance of slow learners by fostering effective study habits. (Princy et al., 2023).

A descriptive study conducted by (Shete & Jadhav) showed that the majority of students—67.8%—had effective study habits. In terms of academic performance, the majority of nursing students—48.7% of second-year students—fall into the 50–60% range, followed by 32.2% in the 61–70% range and 18.4% in the 71–80% range. Nursing students' study habits and

academic performance have a weakly positive correlation ($r = +0.294$).

A descriptive study was published in the Pondicherry Journal of Nursing by KulandairajEdvinaPrincy (2023) assessed study habits and academic performance among 30 final-year nursing students in SRMT richy College of Nursing shows that 33.3% of students had good, 46.6% average, and 20.1% poor study habits. Notably, 66.67% of students achieved first-class academic performance. The study concluded that better study habits are related to higher academic performance, emphasizing the need for nursing interventions to support slow learners through improved study practices (references).

According to Patil and Naik (2022) a descriptive study in the International Journal of Nursing Education assessed the relationship between study habits and academic performance among (152 third-year B.Sc.) nursing students in Navi Mumbai using M.N. Palsane's Study Habit Inventory, results showed a weak positive correlation ($r = 0.294$) between study habits and academic performance. Significant associations were found between academic achievement and demographic variables such as mother's education, travel time, and mode of transportation ($p < 0.05$), indicating these factors may influence students' academic outcomes.

Karl Pearson's formula was used to calculate the correlation between study habits and academic achievement in this study. The results show a weak positive correlation ($r = 0.294$). Sadry Z. and Muzia S. (2019) investigated the connection between study habits and academic performance in EFL students in Afghanistan. This study found a moderately positive correlation ($r = 0.373$) between students' academic achievement and their study habits. (Sayali et al., 2022).

The purpose of the study was to evaluate the final-year nursing students' study habits. 33% of the students had good study habits, 47% had average study habits, and 20% had poor study habits, according to the data analysis. Moghadam MF provided support for this study, and Cheraghiyan B evaluated it using a cross-sectional study. Habits and their relationship with academic performance among 150 nursing students in Abadan. The result showed that the

students 11.3 had unsatisfactory study habits, 80.7% had moderately satisfactory and 8% satisfactory study habits (Princy et al., 2023b).

STUDY HABITS IN PAKISTAN

The study assesses the academic achievement of nursing students in their final year. The findings showed that, out of 30 students, 6 (20%) had distinction, 20 (66.67%) had first class, and 4 (13.33%) had second class. The outcome was comparable to a descriptive study that Reghuram et al. carried out to evaluate the academic performance and study habits of nursing students in Trivandrum. The findings showed that 59.7% of students perform inadequately academically. (Princy et al., 2023b). M. Mirzaeiet. al. (2019) assessed the status of study habits among Iranian students at Kermanshah University of Medical Sciences. Using a probability sampling technique, 300 students from the 2015–2016 year of school were chosen. The Palsane and Sharma Study Habit Inventory was used to obtain data. According to the study's findings, there is a negative correlation between study habits and age ($r = -0.031$) and a positive correlation between study habits and GPA ($r = 0.216$). 82.2% of students have relatively favorable study habits, followed by 11.2% of students have favorable study habits. Because the p-value is less than 0.005.6, the researcher also concluded that students with high GPAs have good study habits. (D et al., 2017).

At Velammal Medical College Hospital and Research Institute in Mumbai, Rajendra R. et al. (2019) carried out an observational study to analyze the study habits of undergraduate medical students. There were 118 final-year medical students in the 21–22 age range. The average of three general medical assessment scores from the final academic year—high achievement $> 70\%$, average - 50-70%, and low $< 50\%$ —were used to compare the students. These scores were obtained from Denis Congos study skills inventory questionnaire. The total score and percentage of students for each domain were memory 61(51.69%), concentration 67(56.77%), notes taking 7 (5.93%), time management 17 (14.40%), test preparation. The researcher concluded that the ability to pay attention in class is the only study

habit showed the significant difference in across the high, medium and low achievers since p value is 0.005(Sayali et al., 2022).

METHODOLOGY

STUDY DESIGN

A correlational study design was employed for this research. The study was conducted at the Institute of Nursing Sciences (INS), Sarhad University of Information Technology and Science, Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. The duration of the study was six months, in accordance with the university's academic criteria. The total population consisted of 500 undergraduate nursing students. A sample size of 218 participants was determined using the Raosoft sampling calculator, based on a 95% confidence interval and a 5% margin of error. Considering a 10% attrition rate, our final sample size is calculated through a formula, resulting in final sample size of 240 participants. A probability-based systematic random sampling technique was used to select the participants for the study. Only undergraduate nursing students enrolled in INS-SUIT who were willingly agreed to participate, signed the informed consent form, had completed at least one academic year, and had a current GPA were included in the study. First-semester nursing students, absent students on the day of data collection, students from other departments, and MSN students were excluded from the study.

DATA COLLECTION TOOL

Data is collected through a Validated Inventory Checklist; Palsane and Sharma Study Habits Inventory (PSSHI) adapted from an open access research study by (Palsane & Sharma, 1989) with reliability coefficient is 0.88 and poses only face validity. Our data involve demographic variables, rating scales and academic performance which we conducted through a validated questionnaire. The data is collected voluntarily from the participants. The information provided by participant is kept confidential by One Time Passkey.

DATA ANALYSIS PROCEDURE

Data is analyzed through Statistical Package for Social Sciences SPSS version 27. Frequencies (n), percentages (%), and standard deviation (SD) are calculated for all variables. Data is displayed in the form of tables, graphs and charts. Normality Test Shapiro Wilk Test and Pearson correlation coefficient test is used to identify correlations and patterns between study habits and academic performance. The scoring criteria is established from an analytical descriptive study by (Rezaie Looyeh et al., 2017) entitled as "The Relationship between the Study habits and the Academic performance of Medical Sciences Students"; the minimum and maximum score were ranging from 0 and 90 respectively while Study habits that scored 60 or higher considered desirable, those that scored between 31 and 59 were considered slightly desirable, and those that scored less than 30 were considered undesirable. (Rezaie Looyeh et al., 2017).

RESULTS/FINDINGS

Table-1: Demographic Data Descriptive Statistics

S.No	Demographic Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Age of Participants			
		17 Years	1	0.4%
		18 Years	6	2.5%
		19 Years	17	7.1%
		20 Years	41	17.1%
		21 Years	46	19.2%
		22 Years	59	24.6%
		23 Years	43	17.9%
		24 Years	9	3.8%
		25 Years	9	3.8%
		26 Years	4	1.7%
		27 Years	5	2.1%

2.	Gender of Participants			
		Male	183	76.3%
		Female	57	23.8%
3.	Semester of Participants			
		2 nd	74	30.8%
		4 th	34	14.2%
		6 th	66	27.5%
		7 th	23	9.6%
		8 th	43	17.9%
4.	Academic Performance of Participants			
		Poor	3	1.3%
		Average	94	39.5%
		Good	141	59.2%
5.	Socio-Economic Status of Participants			
		Low	16	6.7%
		Middle	216	90.0%
		High	8	3.3%
6.	Residence of Participants			
		Home	85	35.4%
		Hostel	155	64.6%

Table-1 shows demographic variables frequencies and percentages of the participants. There were total of 240 participants whom ages were ranging from a minimum of 17 years to a maximum of 27 years old with an average age of 22 years (24.6%). In those participants 76.3% were male while 23.8% were female. There were total of 5 semesters students involved i.e: 2nd, 4th, 6th, 7th, and 8th with respective percentages as 30.8%, 14.2%, 27.5%, 9.6% and 17.9%.

Graph-1 shows Age of the participants in years and percent students of each year

Graph-2 shows Percentage of participants on the basis of gender

Graph-3 shows semester-wise percentages of students

The academic performances of the participants were calculated on the basis of current semester GPA. The mean current GPA was found to be 3.11 with SD = 0.38 with a minimum GPA of 1.76 and a maximum GPA of 3.95. The

percentage of students with poor academic performance were found to be 1.3%, average academic performance was 39.5% and good academic performance was 59.2%.

Table-2 represents mean, standard deviation, maximum and minimum GPA of students Current GPA of the Students

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Current GPA of the Participants	240	1.76	3.95	3.1145	.38720
Valid N (list-wise)	240				

Graph-4 represents Percent Categories of students

In terms of socioeconomic status, 90.0% were belonging to a middle class. 64.6% of the participants were residents of hostel while 35.4% were residents of home. Moreover, the scoring of study habits were ranging from 0 to

90. The mean study habits score was 56 with SD = 11. Study habits were categorized as undesirable, relatively desirable and desirable with respective percentages of 3.8%, 58.3% and 37.9%.

Graph-5 represents percent-wise study habits categories

The Shapiro-wilk test was run through SPSS to find the normality of data. The value of normality for GPA was found as 0.975 while p-value calculated is less than 0.001. Similarly, the

value for study habits scoring was found out to be 0.975 and p-value calculated is less than 0.001. As, data was not normally distributed so,

spearman correlation test was employed to find the correlation.

Now, to find out the correlation between academic performance and study habits, spearman correlation test was employed. The

value of spearman coefficient constant was found as -.006 and p-value=0.924. A very weak negative correlation was found between study habits and academic performance.

Table 3: Shows the Normality tests finding of the study Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Current GPA of the Participants	.092	238	.000	.975	238	.000
Study Habits Scoring	.080	238	.001	.975	238	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Table 4: Shows the significant Negative correlation between study habits and Academic Performance Spearman Correlation

		Current GPA of the Participants	Study_Habits_Scoring
Spearman's rho	Current GPA of the Participants	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.924
		N	238
Study_Habits_Scoring	Study_Habits_Scoring	Correlation Coefficient	-.006
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.924
		N	240

DISCUSSION

The present study aimed to examine the relationship between study habits and academic performance amongst Undergraduate nursing students at Institute of Nursing Sciences, Sarhad University Peshawar. Contrary to expectation and Prevailing literature, the findings revealed a negligible and statistically non-significant negative correlation (Spearman’s $r = -0.006$, $p = 0.924$) suggesting that there is no meaningful association between study habits and academic achievement within this specific population. This results diverges from multiple prior studies that have reported a positive link between structured study habits and academic success.

For instance (Princy et al., 2023) found that nursing students with good or average study habits tended to perform significantly better, with a considerable nursing achieving first class scores. Similarly, (citation) Identifying a week but positive correlation ($r = 0.294$) between study habits and academic performance. (Citation) Further emphasized that additional factors such as maternal education level, travel time and mode of transportation also significantly

influenced academic outcomes. This discrepancy may be due to contextual and demographic differences including educational system, institutional environment or cultural factors which were not controlled in the current study.

Although the current research utilizes the standardized and validated Palsane and Sharma Study Habits Inventory (PSSHI), which demonstrated a strong internal consistency (Cronbach’s $\alpha = 0.88$), it failed to yield statistically significant finding. Interestingly, 37.9% of students were found to have desirable study habits; however, even this subgroup did not a show significant association with higher grade point average (GPA). This suggests that other unmeasured variable may play a more critical role in determining academic outcomes. Potential contributing factors might be including Psychological stress, language barrier, digital literacy, time constraint or even the mode of instruction.

Moreover, more than 90% of participants belonged to a middle socioeconomic background and resident in hostels. While these

sociodemographic variables were not directly analyzed for their impact on academic performance, they may serve as underlying moderators or mediators of academic success. Nursing, being a high demand program that combines theoretical rigor with intensive clinical practice, requires not only effective study habits but also access to mentorship, hands on clinical exposure, emotional resilience and faculty support.

The use of a correlational study design imposes certain limitations, notably its inability to establish causality or detect changes over time. Additionally, reliance on self-reported data introduces the risk of social desirability and recall bias, potentially compromising the accuracy of response. Future research should consider longitudinal study designs and incorporate variables such as emotional well-being, academic stress levels, teacher-student's dynamics, sleep patterns and motivational strategies to comprehensively understand the determinants of academic success.

Despite the absence of a statistically significant association, this study contributes to the ongoing discourse by challenging the assumptions that better study habits alone guarantee improved academic performance. It highlights the complexity of academic achievement in nursing education and underscores the need for a multidimensional approach to student support. Educational policymakers and faculty should be encouraged to integrate holistic development programs, including mentorship, time management workshops, mental health services and adaptive teaching strategies to foster both academic and personal growth among nursing students.

CONCLUSION

The present study aimed to assess study habits and academic performance among BS nursing students. The result revealed that desirable study habits of the students was 37.92%. The Majority of relatively study habits of the students was 58.33%. Academic performance among nursing students, majority were showing 59.24% which indicate good academic performance of the students. The result also revealed as (-.006 and p-value=0.924) very weak negative association

between study habits and academic performance.

Despite its valuable insights, several limitations must be acknowledged. First, the use of a correlational research study design restricts the ability to establish causality between academic performance and study habits. Second, the study was confined to a single public university nursing department students, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other settings.

Future research should include the participants from multiple universities and institutions to enhance diversity and external validity of the results. Additionally, Comparative study could be conducted to examine study habits and academic performance among undergraduate and postgraduate nursing students within the same institution, or to compare results between private and public sector universities. By the incorporation of qualitative methods in future researches could also provide deeper outlook into the underlying factors influencing academic success and study habits among nursing students.

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